

Biodiversity v/s Pollution

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Protection of Biodiversity is everyone's responsibility. Farmers, villagers, Primitive tribes know how to protect this biodiversity. The so called civilized people of present time should learn from them. All should step forward to save this biodiversity.

EFFECT OF POLLUTION ON BIODIVERSITY

Terrestrial Pollution and Effects on Biodiversity:

In the name of development, the roads, the roofs of the houses, the front yard of the are leveled with cement in turn the rain water is not sinking into the ground. Due to this the level of underground water turns low and the moisture on the upper layer is reduced. The life of the microbes, invertebrates such as helminthes, annelids, arthropods etc, live in the earth is in danger due to non-availability of oxygen and low percentage of moisture. As a result, the richness of species is reduced.

Agriculture-Agro-Chemical, Pesticides and Their Effect on Biodiversity:

To achieve Green Revolution in Agriculture, 'man' is using more Agro-chemicals Pesticides and fertilizers resulting land pollution, Environment pollution and effecting the life on the Earth, The use of Pesticides affects the life of carnivores such as birds rats, rabbits, mongooses, snakes which feed on insects of crops, The internal systems like digestive system, nervous system, are in toxicities and finally the organisms die. With this pesticide pollution, species richness of Biodiversity is reduced .It mean the biodiversity is reduced.

Honey bees and Pollution:

The insects help indirectly for the pollination process in, in the process of searching for nectar, without the insects, there is no reproduction in many plants. The use of pesticides may not only destroy the pests and germs, but also kill the insects resulting the slow pollination or zero Pollination.

Radiation Effect on Honey Bees

The Radiation from the 'CELL TOWERS' is affecting the workers-bees Find it difficult to return to their hive after collecting nectar. The Construction of hives wax cells is affected by this. The life the bees is
Question now.

Agriculture-Bt (Bacillus Thuringen Sis-) Effects

To control pests (insects), in agriculture, the production of pest resistant Plants, which could decrease the amount of pesticide used? Bt toxin

is Produced by a bacterium called *Bacillus Thuringiensis* (BT for short). Bt toxin gene has been cloned from the bacteria and been expressed in plants to provide resistance to insects without the need for insecticides; in effect created a bio-pesticide. Examples are Bt cotton, Bt corn, rice, tomato, potato and soybean etc. These works as insecticides. These Bt produce crystals insecticidal proteins which are formed out of CRY gene. Bt toxin protein exist as inactive protoxins, but once an insect ingest the inactive toxin, it is converted into an active form of toxin due to the alkaline pH of the gut which solubilise the crystals. The activated toxin binds to the surface of midgut epithelial cells and creates pores that cause cell swelling and lyses and eventually cause death of the insect. These proteins are the reasons for the destruction of useful insects. In this way there is reducing biodiversity.

Sparrows Crises in Villages

The small birds which are seen in hundreds very commonly in all villages Environment, towns, by building small beautiful nests. The Urbanization RCC roofs disturbed their habitation. To shift their nests to the other places such as the fields .., the cell towers are of no use because they gave polluted atmosphere and radiation effect to the poor creatures. The number of these small birds is at extinct there.

Vulture Crisis in India

Vulture protect in from pollution by eating dead bodies of the animals before they decompose. But unfortunately the vaccinations & hormones injection to animals for more productivity cause the toxin when vulture eats going to die, their number is reduced. The vulture species is in 'Endanger list' according to Red Data Book. Recently a news appeared in ENADU daily that the forest department officers found the evidences of vulture habitation near peddavagu - pranahita River in Adilabad district (7-june-2013 Bejjur Mandal Morliguda Rock Forest)

Cow Dung Beetle

It's a crowding insect. It's main job is decompose the dung and dead bodies of animals. It's smell creature but its job is great that it protect the environment from air, water, land pollution. But the existence of this insect is in danger now It is a vulnerable creature.. turtles species in danger of Extinction Hucksbill, turtle are special for their unbeaten spirit of roaming all the places in the world .But their number is reduced 80% for the last century .One astonishing reason behind this is 'MAN' .Man uses the shells of these turtles In making ornaments. This has become more commercial due to the Selfishness of MAN. There turtle are fed on coral & coral reefs are under Destruction due to the poisonous leakages from ships. list of IUCN As a result their number is at reduce and these are added invulnerable List of IUCN.

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CONCLUSION

In order to let the biodiversity sustain consistently there must not be Geo-air water pollution. In (forming) agriculture, Bio-pesticides to be used in place of chemical Fertilizers to get good yielding of crops. The activities which increase the radiation effect should be stopped. In the other diversities. The environmental balance to be maintained so as to protect the life on the EARTH. For this, Forrest to be grown more and more. MAN' is the cause for all this destruction of Environment .Man has become more Selfish, luxurious and greedy. In the name of development, he is spoiling the Nature' in turn spoiling his own existence and identify.